

ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PAULISTA BRUTALISM

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ABSTRACT

The paper aims to discover the essence of paulista brutalism through an analysis of essential characteristics of the buildings researched. The term brutalism has been used to refer to a widespread selection of modern architecture from the 1950s to the 1980s. The study argues that brutalism in Brazil, although similar in aesthetic to other brutalisms around the world, is native to the country.

A recent *aestheticisation* of brutalism has seen the popularity of these buildings grow on social media. However, there is little knowledge outside Brazil regarding the context of these buildings, their purpose in the urban fabric and how they are inhabited and experienced. The understanding of ethic as *essence* – derived from the word *ethos* – rather than implying a notion of morality, is concerned with the intrinsic nature and essential quality of a material or space. It is such meaning that determines the character of the building, resulting in more than just an aesthetic experience.

Field work in Brazil, which included visiting the buildings and interviewing key academics and architects, was crucial in providing the data required for the analysis of the buildings and their architectural qualities. By observing, documenting, photographing and drawing the buildings first-hand an analysis of three *essential characteristics*, namely the ground plane, monumentality and relationship between light and material – argues for the essence of paulista brutalism.

Keywords: Brutalism, Essence, Ground Plane, Monumentality, Natural Light.

CARACTERÍSTICAS ESSENCIAIS DO BRUTALISMO PAULISTA RESUMO

Este artigo discute a essência do brutalismo paulista, através de três características essenciais, identificadas e analisadas nas obras arquitetônicas pesquisadas pelos autores. O termo brutalismo tem sido empregado numa vasta seleção de obras da arquitetura moderna dos anos 50 a 80. Este estudo propõe que o brutalismo no Brasil – ainda que esteticamente semelhante a outros brutalismos ao redor do mundo – é nativo do país.

O processo recente de *estetização* do brutalismo tem presenciado o aumento de popularidade das obras arquitetônicas, através das redes sociais de comunicação. No entanto, existe pouco conhecimento fora do Brasil a respeito do contexto dessas obras, a relação delas com o entorno urbano, como elas são utilizadas e vivenciadas no dia-a-dia. A compreensão do conceito de *ética* como essência – derivado do termo *etos* – ao invés de sugerir a noção de *moralidade*, se refere à natureza intrínseca e qualidade essencial do material ou espaço. É tal significado que determina o caráter da obra, resultando em algo mais do que simplesmente uma experiência estética.

O trabalho de campo realizado para esta pesquisa – que incluiu a visita a cada uma das obras selecionadas, além de entrevistas com acadêmicos e arquitetos-chaves – foi essencial na obtenção das informações necessárias para a análise das obras e identificação de suas qualidades arquitetônicas. O trabalho de observação, documentação, registro e ilustrações por fotografias e sketches, permitiu a análise e identificação de três características essenciais – *piso plano*, monumentalidade e relacionamento entre iluminação e material. A forma pela qual essas características se relacionam espacialmente constitui a essência do brutalismo paulista.

Palavras-chaves: Brutalismo, Essência, Tratamento do Chão, Monumentalidade, Iluminação Natural.

CARACTERÍSTICAS ESENCIALES DEL BRUTALISMO PAULISTA RESUMEN

El artículo pretende descubrir la esencia del brutalismo paulista a través de un análisis de las características esenciales de los edificios investigados. El término brutalismo se ha utilizado para referir a una selección extensa de la arquitectura moderna de los años 50 a los años 80. El estudio sostiene que el brutalismo en Brasil, aunque similar en estética a otros brutalismos alrededor del mundo, es nativo del país.

Una reciente *estética* del brutalismo ha visto crecer la popularidad de estos edificios en los medios sociales. Sin embargo, hay poco conocimiento fuera de Brasil sobre el contexto de estos edificios, su propósito en el tejido urbano y cómo están habitados y experimentados. La comprensión de la ética como *esencia* – derivada de la palabra *ethos* – en lugar de implicar una noción de moralidad, se refiere a la naturaleza intrínseca y la calidad esencial de un material o un espacio. Es este significado lo que determina el carácter del edificio, resultando en algo más que solamente una experiencia estética.

El trabajo de campo en Brasil, que incluyó visitar los edificios y entrevistar a académicos y arquitectos, fue crucial para proporcionar los datos necesarios para el análisis de los edificios y sus cualidades arquitectónicas. Al observar, documentar, fotografiar y dibujar los edificios de primera mano un análisis de tres *características esenciales*, es decir, el tratamiento del suelo, la monumentalidad y la relación entre la luz y el material – aboga por la esencia del brutalismo paulista.

Palabras-claves: Brutalismo, Esencia, Tratamiento del suelo, Monumentalidad, Luz Natural.

The aim of this paper is to provide an understanding of paulista brutalism through the definition and analysis of essential characteristics identified in the buildings researched.

With a growing *aestheticisation* of brutalism, predominantly through social media, brutalist buildings in Brazil are gaining more international interest. However, this is solely through images, which are limited in the information they can reveal to the viewer. There is little knowledge outside Brazil regarding the context of these structures, their purpose in the urban fabric and how these buildings are inhabited and experienced.

The label *brutalism* has not always been accepted by architects in Brazil. Most notably, Vilanova Artigas was concerned in protecting and expressing the fundamentals of an architecture that was inherently Brazilian, and could be “a symbol of a country's political and cultural emancipation, leading to economic development” (FRAMPTON, WISNIK, 2010, p. 12). Brazilian architects were resistant to connect their architecture to an international discourse, as their preoccupation was to propose an architecture representing a national identity. Sergio Ferro, a student of Artigas, did not deny the existence of a foreign influence when he wrote: “We swallowed brutalism and transformed it in a cannibalistic and caboclo attitude” (FRAMPTON, WISNIK, 2010, p. 12-13). The term *caboclo* is Portuguese for a person of mixed indigenous Brazilian and white European ancestry. Using Ferro's explanation and Artigas's views, Brazilian brutalism is certainly native in its conception, distancing itself from British brutalism, to the extent that the term *brutalism* was retrospectively applied to Brazilian architecture.

With this in mind, the research endeavoured to understand Brazilian brutalism from a native perspective – through desktop studies of Brazilian publications, visits to the buildings and meetings with architects and academics in Brazil. I cannot, however, ignore my own background: as a student at Newcastle University (one of the origins of brutalism in Britain, where Alison and Peter Smithson studied); whose last year's design studio focused on brutalism (reading Banham and the Smithsons to re-appropriate a brutalist factory in Rotterdam); and having been tutored and supervised by Steve Parnell, a brutalist enthusiast (with publications on brutalism including “The Meanings of Concrete: Introduction”, in *The Journal of Architecture* and “Charles & Ray Eames, The Proto-Brutalists”, in *World of Charles And Ray Eames*).

My research, therefore, was focused towards understanding the differences and similarities between British and Brazilian brutalism.

Research into the Brazilian context, via online resources and the archive of Brazilian journals and periodicals at the Riba Library, was crucial in grasping an insight into the architectural climate of the time to understand how the buildings were critiqued and discussed during their epoch. The reading of journals such as *Acrópole*, *Módulo* and *Projeto*, used along with websites like www.sosbrutalism.org, archdaily.com.br, www.arquiteturabrutalista.com.br, and www.fuckyeahbrutalism.tumblr.com, allowed me to select buildings to be visited in Brazil during fieldwork in the summer of 2016. The selection considered buildings from different regions of Brazil; from different architects; covering different time periods; and of different building typologies. A total of 28 buildings were visited, of which 13 were in São Paulo.

Brutalism in Brazil may be chronologically and aesthetically similar to the various other brutalisms illustrated in *The New Brutalism: Ethic or Aesthetic?* by Reyner Banham. However, different from European and American brutalism, which are rooted in the ethics and aesthetics of the trauma and immediate hope of a post war era, (van den Heuvel, 2015, p. 293) the Brazilian context stems from another origin, due to the effect of the war having much less of an impact in Brazil. The buildings themselves have a different organisation of space and relationship to public/private and inside/outside space, compared to brutalist architecture in the UK, not only due to the socio-economic and political climate in which they were designed and built, but also due to its tropical environment.

The paper aims to present an analysis of paulista brutalism. It does not intend to achieve a wide sweeping conclusion through a limited selection of buildings, but instead focuses on key characteristics which were identified in the buildings selected, in order to reveal what brutalism means in the context of São Paulo and in doing so, provide further avenues for research.

As Prof. Ruth Verde Zein states in her book *Brutalist Connections*:

In architecture, perhaps the most important documents are the buildings themselves – and they too, are patiently waiting for our reflections. They are mute but indefatigable, and no one will ever be able to exhaust their potential: at any time a fresh look will extract other perceptions and devise new ideas. (ZEIN, 2014, p. 24)

Before discussing the essential characteristics, which form the core of this paper, this section will look at the theoretical framework of the research, as an attempt to understand the differences and similarities between British and Brazilian brutalism.

The main protagonists of the discussion on brutalism in Britain were Reyner Banham and Alison and Peter Smithson – this is not to say that there were no others involved, but their viewpoints are crucial to understand the discussion between ethic and aesthetic.

In his now famous *Architectural Review* article of December 1955, Reyner Banham defines new brutalism as: 1. Memorability as an Image; 2. Clear exhibition of Structure; and 3. Valuation of Materials 'as found'. (BANHAM, 1955, p. 361) He clearly pointed to an aesthetic angle of his criteria with the focus on *image*. In his 1966 book *The New Brutalism: Ethic or Aesthetic?* he stated that "Brutalism never quite broke out of the aesthetic frame of reference" (BANHAM, 1966, p. 134). The emphasis on the aesthetic aspects is evident in his book through the use of captivating images and photographs of the buildings and their material expression (PARNELL, 2015, p. 98-103).

The Smithsons, however, saw the core of the new brutalism as ethical. In an article published in the *Architectural Design*, in 1957, they explained that any debate on brutalism would be misconstrued if it did not appreciate brutalism's effort to be "objective about *reality* – the cultural objectives of society, its urges, and so on" (SMITHSON, SMITHSON, 1957, p. 113). They concluded that discussions on brutalism had been centred on style and aesthetics, but "its essence is ethical" (SMITHSON, SMITHSON, 1957, p. 113). The Smithsons' focus on reality and creating "poetry out of the confused and powerful" (SMITHSON, SMITHSON, 1957, p. 113). is very similar to Artigas's "critical attitude towards reality" (CONTIER, ANELLI, 2015, p. 465) and using architecture to reveal the struggles within Brazilian society.

The understanding of materials expressed by the Smithsons is shown in the qualities of the *As Found*, which they see as the true essence of the material: "the woodness of wood; the sandiness of sand" (VAN DEN HEUVEL, 2015, p. 301). This identifies a key component of brutalism for the Smithsons, which focusses not on the material itself, but on how it is handled to express the quality of the material. Peter Smithson later explained it as: "there is a way of handling gold in brutalist manner and it does not mean rough and cheap, it means: what is its raw quality?" (HEUVEL, 2015, p. 301).

The Smithsons explained brutalism as a narrative on ordinary everyday life, where they defined the *as found* as stripping back to the *ordinary*. The appreciation of the everyday is shared by Paulo Mendes da Rocha in his critique of the unnecessary use of new and expensive technologies and materials, for the purpose of showing off. He believes that the best architectural techniques are not spectacular, but strive to best facilitate “our lives and our daily performance.” (Architecture: Interview, 2008)

The question of brutalism being an ethic is difficult to argue in terms of stating that all architects shared an ethical standpoint, which manifested itself as a collective aesthetic. However, the idea of ethic as *essence* is a far more subtle and deeply-seated understanding of the word, which relates to the treatment of materials, structure, light and space. Ethic as essence would allow for an ethic to exist within brutalism, without needing to have a shared ethical standpoint. The two meanings of *ethic*, often confused in brutalist discourse, are:

- Ethic as a set of moral principles, where architecture and buildings become a manifesto for a certain way of life.
- Ethic as *essence*, derived from the word *ethos*, rather than implying a morality, is concerned by the intrinsic nature and essential quality of a material or space, which determines its character, resulting in more than just an aesthetic experience.

I have complemented Banham's three characteristics of British brutalism mentioned above with three essential characteristics of Brazilian brutalism:

1. Treatment of the Ground Plane;
2. Monumentality and Scale;
3. The Relationship Between Natural Light and Material.

The characteristics were derived from fieldwork observations and conversations with academics and architects, to determine not only what characteristics are shared by the buildings but also the characteristics which differentiate the buildings from other brutalisms.

ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTIC 1: THE GROUND PLANE

The ground plane is often a moment of transition: between public space and private space; between designed and undesigned space; and from leaving the ground to ascend or descend into the building.

The Brazilian Pavilion for the Osaka World Fair of 1970, designed by Paulo Mendes da Rocha, in collaboration with Flávio Motta, Júlio Katinsky, Ruy Ohtake and Jorge Caron, highlights the ground plane as a key characteristic of its architecture. The jury indicated that the design achieved “the liberation of the ground, with an elaborate ground treatment on composition of space rich in forms and content” (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343). Zein comments that:

the treatment of the ground as spatial composition is undoubtedly one of the strengths of the paulista brutalist architecture, which does not *land* delicately in place but, perhaps due to the undulating topography of local geography, it is always required to design and shape the floor (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343).

She goes on to argue that although the treatment of the ground plane is not unique to brutalism in Brazil, it is difficult to claim that it is as key a characteristic of the Carioca school, and other modern Brazilian architecture, as it is in brutalism (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343).

SUPPORT POINT AND STRUCTURE

The contact between the building and the ground plane is crucial to the creation of space and the monumentality of the building. The support point is often well considered and expressed. The structural columns are often thinned at the point of contact with the ground plane and make use of the sculptural and plastic quality of concrete, in an expression of the building's connection to its site. As well as thinning the connection, the points of contact themselves are often minimised to create spatial permeability.

The Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism at the University of São Paulo (FAU USP), by Vilanova Artigas and Carlos Cascaldi, draws attention to the skilled engineering in the sculptural structure, in contrast with the unskilled labour seen in the rough concrete mass it supports. The large building is only supported on its external façade by 14 columns which free the corners. The columns are two intersecting triangles which thin in the middle, and appear different when viewed from straight on and from the side.

An earlier building by Vilanova Artigas and Carlos Cascaldi is the Anhembi Tênis Clube, where their structural solution has similarities

to FAU USP. Although not to the same scale and not creating the same sense of weightlessness, there is still a strong sculptural and plastic quality in the columns – consisting of two intersecting triangles, with the column continuing in the roof structure above.

The Museum of Art of São Paulo – Masp by Lina Bo Bardi minimises the contact with the ground plane – with only four columns supporting the building mass and creating a public space below. The building consists of two parts: the hanging concrete and glass box; and the submerged volume underneath – with the public space sandwiched between the two. The ground plane, therefore, is the centre of the building and the relationship between the two parts of the building can only be appreciated in section.

Paulo Mendes da Rocha's first major work was the gymnasium of the Paulistano Athletic Club, in 1957. The key architectural qualities of Mendes da Rocha's design were: 1) The small contact point with the ground of the large concrete structures, visible from inside and outside; 2) The slenderness of the canopy – allowing light to flood into the gymnasium below; and 3) No threshold between external/internal, creating a strong relationship with the building and its surrounding. Changes to the original design have stripped the building of its architectural qualities by adding annex spaces around the perimeter, as the structure below the canopy is no longer visible, and therefore the contact point of the structure with the ground cannot be seen.

The structural understanding, which is manifested aesthetically in the sculptural columns, is the result of strong relationships between some very good structural engineers and the architects. Zein describes it as an understanding which enables a two-way creative direction, and compares it to the professional relationship between Louis Kahn and August Komendant:

we had the same devotions and practically no misfortune, we dreamed together, we built together; [Kahn] was full of ideas, and anything of an advanced, new concept was interesting to him [...] because we both had the attitude that structure is an integral part of architecture. All the buildings we designed were structure - what else? But structure conformed in such a way that it became architecture. (ZEIN, 2005, p. 95)

APPROACH, ENTRANCE AND CIRCULATION CONTINUATION OF GROUND PLANE

The entrance is the moment of transition from the ground plane into the building. Depending on the treatment of the threshold, there is potential to create a continuation of the ground plane within the building. Once the ground plane has been continued to the inside space, it can be lost through the internal circulation. Some of the buildings, however, have designed the circulation for the ground plane to continue past the ground floor. One way to continue the ground plane within the building is through the treatment of the ponto de apoio (support point). In many of the buildings visited, the carefully considered columns lift the building mass from the ground plane, providing a flow into the internal space and creating a permeability and blurring between inside and outside space, without marking a threshold.

The structural treatment of FAU creates a permeability at the ground plane, while having an impermeable façade above, which opens as you enter, to express the uses on the various levels. There is no threshold – only a change of height as you pass under the concrete level above and are released into the full-height naturally-lit atrium. The spatial continuity of the building is seen in its circulation, which consists of ramps connecting the offset half levels on either side, all orientated around the central atrium: “With neither doors nor interruptions, one passes from the city to the studios on the upper level.” (CONTIER, ANELLI, 2015, p. 465) The spatial generosity, created by the structure, is made political through Artigas's discourse: “This building reflects the worthy ideals of today: I saw it as spatialization of democracy, in dignified spaces, without front doors – a temple where all activities are valid.” (ARTIGAS, PUNTONI, 1997, p. 101)

In some buildings, the architect has designed a continuation of the ground plane through an entrance which marks a journey from the approach to the building and throughout it. The São Bonifácio Church, was designed by Hans Broos, with his focus being the journey from the street to the altar. The building is lifted off the ground on thin pillars on one side and a service core and circulation on the other. It is entered through a ramp and shallow steps, which run beside each other in a double/triple height space. The ramp creates a continuity from the outside space, and the glass and stained glass draw in natural light focusing attention to the internal concrete materiality. As you ascend to the first floor, the focus of the connection to

the outside changes to focusing on the church as an isolated space itself, with no external interference. Although the continuation of public space was key to Broos' original design, the addition of a security fence, which restricts the access to the building to church service hours only, imposes a boundary of public/private space.

The José Antônio Filippelli Residence, by Ruy Ohtake, is firmly fixed in its site, with the architect using the full width of the plot, creating a concrete partition wall leading you to the entrance with a cantilevered concrete wall above. Ohtake creates a journey within the house and a strong connection to the ground plane by using the house to connect the two levels of the sloped site – the entrance on the ground level and the back garden on the first floor.

The continuation of the ground plane is achieved in these buildings due to the careful design of the approach, the entrance and, in some cases, the circulation of the building. Maria Sanvitto talks about the ethic of spatial organisation and how paulista brutalism believed in truth, correctness, virtue and equality of men, which interpreted into architecture, meant that there was nothing to hide, resulting in single spaces where segregation was not accepted and compartmentalisation was avoided: (SANVITTO, 2013, p. 11) "It defended the single space as freedom over privacy that compartmentalization can offer. The private was somehow associated with the wrongdoing." (SANVITTO, 2013, p. 12) The observations collected through this research indicate that these concepts also have significance in not just the internal spatial organisation, but also the spatial continuity and relationship between the outside, public realm and the building.

INSIDE/OUTSIDE AND PUBLIC/PRIVATE SPACE

The ground plane is often used to bring public space into the building, with minimal thresholds creating a blurring of inside/outside. There is often an integrated experience between inside and outside – making use of a space which is neither one nor the other – the experience of the building involves its surroundings, which several academics suggested is because of the tropical climate of Brazil. (ZEIN, 2016; CASTELLOTTI, 2016)

The public space is very important in MASP, as the ground plane is between the two levels supported above and the two levels submerged below. Masp stands out on Paulista avenue, not just because

of its vibrant red colour, or its impressive unsupported span, but as a public space and a building that has a strong connection to the ground plane, amongst a wall of high-rise skyscrapers. The public space is underneath a suspended mass of raw concrete; however, the space feels open and unoppressive, and becomes a space often used for arts and crafts markets, concerts and exhibitions.

ARTIFICIAL VERSUS NATURAL

All buildings must deal with nature, whether they choose to accept it or reject it. Throughout the buildings researched there seemed to be a strong connection between these man-made brutalist works and their surrounding environment. The connection between inside and outside space can often create this relationship, which Zein attributes to the openness of the access resulting in a strong visual relationship with the environment. (ZEIN, 2005, p. 33-34) This also impacts the image of brutalism in Brazil which is often framed within a natural setting with trees, mountains, and the sky – creating a dialogue between these two opposites, the concrete building and nature.

The Escola Jardim Ipê, although now disconnected from its original site and outdoor space, was conceived through the idea of creating a building which married its natural setting, as described by Decio Tozzi in his website:

This design idea is always characteristic of each case, of each project. It assumes, therefore, a particularized accent, valuing the careful consideration of all the elements that make up the physical and human picture of the place as a constructed and natural landscape. (Escola Jardim Ipê)

The José Antônio Filippelli Residence is very fixed in its site and has a strong relationship to both gardens, but particularly the back garden which comes directly off the large open-plan living and dining space, partitioned by glazed doors, making the transition seamless. The qualities of light also reinforce the connection with nature and will be analysed further in the following section.

The Anhembi Tennis Club also incorporates rainwater drainage into its design, by integrating it into its structure – however, the later addition of drainage pipes has affected the aesthetic simplicity of

the feature. The structure also includes voids for natural light, which strengthen the buildings connection to nature.

When analysing the connection between building and nature three different aspects were identified: 1) the strong dialogue with its site, while including nature within the building; 2) the use of water drainage as a feature of the building; and 3) natural light being brought into the building. As well as these aspects, the forming and the markings of the concrete itself leaves a physical imprint of nature on the surface of the material as its finished aesthetic.

The ground plane is very important in creating the relationship between a building and its environment – whether it be the earth from where the plants and trees grow, or the end destination of the rainwater that falls on them, these buildings all create a strong dialogue between themselves and their surroundings.

SUMMARY

The ground plane is often used to bring public space into the building, with minimal thresholds creating a blurring of inside/outside – and in doing so strengthening the connection with the surrounding context and the natural elements. The ground plane and how it is used by these buildings, enables them to become part of the urban fabric of their cities, as opposed to simply habitable sculptures.

The connection between public and private space is now becoming rare in São Paulo, and something which makes the brutalist buildings stand out is the way the public space is often open and utilised. It is also the first principle of the architecture that is nowadays lost by fencing off and privatizing the buildings, creating thresholds between inside and outside which were not original to the design and in fact designed to not exist. The threat and/or fear of lack of security in São Paulo has resulted in a culture of creating strong boundaries.

It is this openness that was designed by the architects in the '50s, '60s and '70s which has created a relationship with the ground plane and the internal space. This essential characteristic is different to that of brutalism in the UK, and possibly the Northern Hemisphere, due to Brazil's climate, which is translated into its brutalist architecture. The different climate no doubt plays a major role in the way brutalism is expressed in Brazil, compared to Britain – but there are other aspects that need to be taken into consideration, such as the socio-economic and political context, not forgetting the cultural aspect of a more outgoing society.

The RIBA's criteria of "What to look for in a brutalist building" includes "Heavy-looking materials" and "Massive forms" (Brutalism, n.d.) as two of the five characteristics, which both result in a sense of monumentality. Monumentality, therefore, is not unique to paulista brutalism in distinguishing it from other brutalisms. The way in which monumentality is achieved, however, may be different and its importance as a key characteristic cannot be ignored.

In 1944 Louis Kahn described monumentality as: "a spiritual quality inherent in a structure which conveys the feeling of its eternity, that it cannot be added to or changed." (KAHN, 2003, p. 21) The quality of monumentality in paulista brutalism is very similar in the way concrete is used to affirm political strength, ideas and manifestos for change, as well as proposing an alternative architectural identity – which requires memorable buildings, which are often monumental.

LIFTING HEAVY MASS AND STRUCTURE

The analysis of the ground plane highlighted the importance of the *ponto de apoio* (support point) and structure in lifting a heavy mass from the ground and creating a sense of monumentality – with either the slenderness of the supports or the minimised number of them exaggerating the heavy mass they support.

As analysed earlier, FAU USP is a very good example of how the point of contact with the ground creates a juxtaposition between the heavy mass and the light supports that are able to lift it from the ground plane and create monumentality. By freeing the corners of supports, and minimising the thickness and number of them, the visual disparity between the building's mass and its supports is exaggerated. Felipe Contier and Renato Anelli explain that:

Artigas mixes the truth of materials and structural behaviour with the figurative tradition of Latin American monumentality. Thus, the visual effect of the structure is more radical than its effective rationalisation. (CONTIER, ANELLI, 2015, p. 469)

Although lifted from the ground differently to FAU USP, the São Bonifácio Church establishes its monumentality in a similar manner. It

is further exaggerated by the building being completely lifted off the ground plane and creating external public space underneath. Masp creates a sense of monumentality very similarly, only at a larger scale. In the case of Masp especially, being lifted off the ground plane, the building becomes monumental, even though it is surrounded by buildings of a similar or larger scale.

The relationship between an exaggerated heavy mass, often of a wide span and supported off the ground, contrasted with the minimal structure on which it sits, creates a sense of monumentality, which is further accentuated due to the concrete mass being overhead.

EXAGGERATED SCALE

Another tactic used to create a sense of monumentality is through the exaggeration of scale. The following examples highlight how an exaggerated scale of volumetric space and physical building elements can create a sense of monumentality.

The central atrium of FAU USP gives the internal space the same monumentality that the building's exterior creates. The internal courtyard is given real importance due to the large void - connecting all the spaces of the building. The rigid, geometric box of the exterior is contrasted to the spatial freedom within the building, and both are of a monumental scale.

Zein explains the unique challenge of sacred architecture when dealing with modern architecture, due to its eminently secular character. The contradiction comes between the eagerness to break away from the past and the unavoidable requirement to respect, renew and transform the tradition of sacred spaces (ZEIN, 2005, p. 326). Hans Broos was faced with this challenge in designing the São Bonifácio Church, where there is a disconnection to the human scale which creates monumentality and, in doing so, highlights the importance of the sacred space. The São Bonifácio Church makes use of a double height space, which is completely introverted, apart from natural light entering from above.

The exaggerated scale of building elements, especially with concrete forms, draws attention to them due to their increased weight. The composition of these building elements, depending on how they are supported and their relationship with the rest of the building, can create a sense of monumentality, as seen in the structure of the gymnasium at the Paulistano Athletic Club.

The examples above demonstrate how an exaggerated scale of volumetric space through creating voids and large openings, as well as exaggerated building elements, serve to create a disconnection from the human scale and can therefore feel monumental.

SCALE, COMPRESSION AND RELEASE

Scale is a comparative notion, therefore to fully appreciate the monumentality of these structures the human scale becomes important. These monumental buildings can relate to the human scale through the architect's attention to detail in terms of compression of spaces, as well as design of furniture, fixtures and fittings that are tactile with delicacy that contrasts the scale and roughness of concrete.

In the previous 'essential characteristic', the entrance sequence to FAU-USP is explained as not having a threshold – instead, the concrete volume above creates a moment of compression as you enter the building, before being released into the central atrium.

The program of the building is also important, as highlighted by Rodrigo Cerviño Lopez, director of Tocoa Arquitectos and former student at FAU USP, who admits being heavily influenced by São Paulo's brutalism. He explained the connection between monumentality and the scale of the program:

A building which is large due to its function is naturally monumental and then the difficulty is the introduction of the human scale. Smaller buildings, however, for example houses, already have a human scale and it is through the building's poetic character, achieved by 'strong design and assertive architecture' where a sense of monumentality can exist. (LOPEZ, 2016)

The José Antônio Filippelli Residence, by Ruy Ohtake, is a good example where monumentality is achieved on that basis. The house is entered under the concrete cantilevered first floor, creating a moment of compression before entering a double-height space. The rooms in the house are relatively small, with the open plan living and dining space, which leads out to the back garden with a fully glazed façade, creating a contrast. The furniture is all made from concrete with shelving units, a dining table, a coffee table and a seating area all sharing the

same materiality of the structure and external aesthetic of the house, with the use of concrete throughout all scales of the design.

Designing to a human scale is the fundamental principle of architecture as we are the building users, and spend most our lives in houses which often do not have a sense of monumentality. Therefore, it is the exception to experience a space in which we feel overwhelmed by its scale. By creating moments in architecture which juxtapose the human and the monumental scale, the experience is intensified due to being released into the space.

SUMMARY

The notion of a building program having an innate scale or sense of monumentality relates to symbolism and the associations of building typologies. (LOPEZ, 2016) However, through the design, the architect can accentuate the inherent monumentality through the techniques of lifting a heavy mass; exaggerating scale and space; and creating juxtapositions of scale. The architecture of sacred spaces is a typology which, by its very function and symbolism, has a sense of monumentality, and is often harnessed by the architect to draw out its monumental qualities in the challenge of creating a modern building for a function with traditional values.

The materiality of concrete itself, through its rough and raw aesthetic, has a heaviness that, whether lifted off the ground or exaggerated in scale, creates an overwhelming sense of monumentality. There is also an enduring quality of concrete that provides these buildings with the sense that they have existed for a long time, and will be there for a long time to come, which contributes to an essence of monumentality due to its longevity. Monumentality alone is insufficient for a building to be considered brutalist. It is through the other 'essential characteristics' which share connections with the essence of monumentality – through the connection with the ground plane and the support point, and also natural light as a tool to emphasise monumentality – that one can understand what constitutes paulista brutalism.

ESSENTIAL CHARACTERISTIC 3: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NATURAL LIGHT AND MATERIAL

In discussing the *essential characteristics*, the subject of light has already been mentioned regarding the natural qualities of daylight

and its relationship with the buildings. This section particularly analyses its potential to create and enhance the internal spatial environment. Masao Furuyama, in his book on Tadao Ando, explains the transformative power of light on architecture: "Then, suddenly, here comes light. Symbolic light, embodied light. Light that, in a breath, transforms pure space into dramatic space. Light and shadow impart movement to space, loosen its tension, and endow geometric space with corporeality." (FURUYAMA, 1996, p. 13) This section deals with 'natural light' as an essential characteristic, analysing how the buildings are designed to bring in natural light and how it enhances and transforms the internal space and materiality.

Despite many of the examples discussed having a strong continuation of the ground plane, there is often limited visual connection to the outside, with openings seen as opportunities to bring light in, rather than offer views out. In her PhD, Ruth Verde Zein creates an "Alphabet of Characteristics for Paulista Brutalist Architecture" where "U" characterises two light qualities as being; natural light openings to the side, which are usually shaded, resulting in a weak and diffuse natural illumination at the edges; contrasting with zenithal openings which flood central spaces with natural light (ZEIN, 2005, p. 34). Whilst British brutalism often intends to flood internal spaces with natural light, in order to maximise the quality of sunlight, it can be said that due to Brazil's specific climate, the use of diffuse light is particularly prevalent in a search for shade. Daylight is used for orientation in both time and place, and therefore diffuse light allows this, while protecting the space from the intense sunlight of the day, creating cool, ethereal spaces which exaggerate the concrete materiality.

AMBIENT LIGHT

Ambient light is characterised as openings which create a similar light condition to that of outside. Juhani Pallasmaa writes that:

Natural light plays a vital role in the symphony of our senses, is a precondition for human health, and gives us a sense of space and time. Yet, most of the time, we are unaware of its importance and take its presence for granted. Great works of art and architecture have the potential to change this. They let us experience light in all its nuances and colours, feel its interaction with material and space. (PALLASMAA, 2016)

By capturing the unassuming character of natural light, the architecture draws attention to its qualities.

The roof of FAU USP is a grid of skylights bathing the top levels and atrium space with natural light. The internal spaces are organised by their need for different qualities of light – with studios on the top floor in need of the natural light, while office spaces, the library and teaching rooms requiring more control and therefore need artificial lighting. In Yves Bruand's book *Arquitetura Contemporânea No Brasil* (Contemporary Architecture in Brazil) in describing FAU USP he states: "Here, brutalism is total, materially and spiritually." (BRUAND, 1981, p. 302) The quality of light in FAU USP is rich due to the entire roof being permeable to light, creating a unique and even spiritual atmosphere, which celebrates the spatial freedom contained within the closed concrete box.

Artigas and Cascaldi's earlier design, the Anhembi Tennis Club, also introduces light through the concrete roof structure, creating an even quality of light within the sports spaces, as it illuminates the activity and the concrete structure.

The design for Escola Jardim Ipê is focused around bringing light into the classrooms and the internal patio via skylights. The form of the skylights themselves result in giving the whole building a unique form, driven from the practicalities of bringing in diffuse light. On his website, Decio Tozzi reflects on the theoretical point of the project being the research of space and light (Escola Jardim Ipê, n.d.); and although the school has gone through changes which have affected the original architectural qualities of the design, the quality of light remains.

Ruy Ohtake uses the full width of the plot at the José Antônio Filippelli Residence, with no openings on the concrete façade of the first floor. To introduce light into the spaces there are 1.5m openings along each side, allowing light to enter between the concrete structure and creating private garden spaces for the bedrooms, which are fully glazed, allowing the light to enter into the bedroom spaces too.

INTENTIONAL LIGHT

Natural light is also used in paulista brutalism to direct attention to particular moments of the architecture, with the intentional light creating a hierarchy within the space.

In the São Bonifácio Church natural light, brought in from openings above, washes the side walls while expressing the concrete

structure and materiality. There are additional skylights above the altar running the full width of the church, bathing the altar and the cross in natural light. Although this can be seen as an example of both types of light due to the general lighting quality on the altar, the use of the direct light, to highlight symbolic elements within the building, implies that this is not intended for general dwelling, but for both religious and spatial orientation.

SUMMARY

Pallasmaa explains the relationship of place and light:

Every distinct space and place has its characteristic light, and light is often the quality that most directly conditions our mood. Light is the strongest conditioner of the atmosphere of place, the most comprehensive criteria of the character of space, place and setting (PALLASMAA, 2016).

The separations of *ambient light* and *intentional light* have served to accentuate a quality which can be argued to particularly serve the identity of Brazilian brutalism – the use of light in the context of the Brazilian climate. This speaks to the particular need for daylight in orientation, symbolic lighting in creation of atmosphere, but without the need for constant and strong daylight to illuminate the space. Light also becomes a tool to mediate between the user and the building, by adding a further layer of atmosphere and experience.

The difference between natural light as opposed to artificial light is important due to the ever-changing and living quality of daylight, contrasting with artificial light which is lifeless and even if made to change, it is predetermined and controlled. Henry Plummer, author of *The Architecture of Natural Light and Poetics of Light*, explains daylight as;

a creative tool in architecture that has moods, which are able to infuse physical things with a metaphysical spirit, and can totally alter the character of a building. ... Without the atmospheric presence of daylight, buildings might be able to support our bodies but they would never be able to sustain our spirits – something we require as human beings (Light Matters, n.d.).

The power of light draws out the qualities of materials – the materiality acts as a canvas to these changing light qualities. Pallasmaa argues that: “All sensory experiences are, fundamentally, experiences of touch; we touch with our eyes, ears, nose and tongue as much as we do with our skin.” (PALLASMAA, 2016) And therefore light is the tool which allows us to feel the materiality and texture of the buildings with our eyes. The relationship between light and material is what differentiates the quality of light in Brazilian brutalism from that of Modernism in Brazil. The light and shadow on a raw and rough surface has far greater depth and richness than when it hits painted and polished surfaces.

Pallasmaa explains that: “The experiences of matter, space and light are inseparable. And there is no true architectural experience without light.” (PALLASMAA, 2016) This relates to the strong connection between the earlier essential characteristics and that of natural light. Similar to the ground plane, the importance of light can be seen as the desire to create a connection between inside and outside. The experience of monumentality within architecture is often heightened and brought to attention through the use of natural light. This is particularly noticeable in those buildings of religious use, when light plays an important role in promoting monumentality.

CONTEMPORARY EXAMPLES

When discussing the essence of paulista brutalism, it is worth considering not only the future use of the buildings themselves, but the architecture which has since been inspired by its ‘essential characteristics’. This leads us to examples of contemporary architecture which find themselves reacting to this definitive style.

Although not directly discussed within this paper, the contemporary buildings visited in Brazil share very similar characteristics to those outlined as the essential ones. Two buildings by Tacoa Arquitetos, Galeria Adriana Verajão (2004-2008) and Vila Aspícueta (2010-2013), as well as Galeria Leme (2011-2012), by Paulo Mendes da Rocha and Metro Arquitetos, are of particular interest in the way they relate to the ‘essential characteristics’ analysed above.

The question of a *contemporary brutalism* was mentioned when interviewing Rodrigo Cerviño Lopez, from Tacoa Arquitetos. The architect stated how his main influence was Vilanova Artigas and explained how studying at FAU USP and therefore, entering the building every day, was a key influence. He also explained how he has always

liked the architecture of the 60s, 70s and 80s, and how growing up in São Paulo references you to what is *good architecture* by the very buildings of Masp, MuBE, FAU, Sesc Pompeia, etc. He concluded by saying: "We come from a tradition of research and work of this material [concrete], since Niemeyer and the whole paulista school. So, I come from a mountain of people that came before me, who researched and used concrete a lot, creating a long tradition" (Lopez, 2016).

When referring to FAU USP, Paulo Mendes da Rocha uses an analogy:

Initially Flavio Motta and Vilanova Artigas were responsible for this particular assembly of knowledge, which is also similar to putting together a kind of squad. Therefore, as Father Antonio Vieira says, the tree has roots, trunks, branches, limbs, leaves, flowers, and fruits. I look at FAU that way, like Vieira's tree. And I see myself as one of these fruits (WISNIK, 2008, p. 135) .

The imagery used by Mendes da Rocha can be taken even further and used to understand this idea of *contemporary brutalism*. It is not the same brutalism of the earlier period, but many of the architects are part of the same *tree*- just as Paulo Mendes da Rocha with the seeds of his *fruit*, through teaching and collaboration, strongly influences a younger generation of architects in São Paulo.

CONCLUSION

The Brazilian Pavilion of the 1970 Osaka World Fair is a key building in demonstrating brutalism as architecturally representing the country's identity. The jury commented that: "the winning project chose a distinctly Brazilian approach [...] its greater sense of depth is an unmistakable poetics, closely linked to the Brazilian traditions" (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343). If the Brazilian Pavilion was to be analysed similarly to the buildings researched in this study, it would highlight the three essential characteristics as being the key qualities of its architecture. The ground plane is crucial to the design: "the liberation of the ground, with an elaborate ground treatment on composition of space rich in forms and content" (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343). Its undulating form creates different spaces submerged underneath and the outside space itself, which establishes a dialogue with the concrete

form above, due to its changing levels and three of the four support points being hidden within the ground. Its monumentality is striking and stands out against the other pavilions due to its materiality of concrete and its inherent permanence, contrasted by the temporary pavilions alongside it. The qualities of natural light are very similar to FAU USP in the way the roof becomes fully permeable as a grid of sky-lights. The pavilion certainly had an impact on the spread of a brutalist fashion, with widespread dissemination throughout Brazil by the 1970s (ZEIN, 2005, p. 343).

There is an interesting relationship between the characteristic of the ground plane and the characteristic of the control of light. Each one creates a connection to the outside; however, the presence of both immerses the building with the qualities of outside through the physical connection of the ground plane and the ethereal quality of natural light. The fact that these buildings often lack a visual connection to their surroundings is interesting – as the experience in the space may be more powerful than the visible surroundings themselves. When talking about FAU, Paulo Mendes da Rocha says: “there is no artist who doesn't want an illuminated ceiling [...] The light, the sun, the moon, the stars, the sky, are beautiful inspirations to make a building, so the whole ceiling seems as if it is made of crystal” (ARTIGAS, 2015).

The experience of the building is something which connects all three essential characteristics, due to the internal space acting as a continuation of the outside – through the ground plane and control of light. The use of scale to create monumentality adds another layer of an experiential quality, as it can create a connection and disconnection between the person and the building.

It can be said that paulista brutalism includes some ethical discourse in certain built examples and by certain architects, however the whole body of work cannot be described through this one ethical underpinning. It is through the construction and analysis of *essential characteristics* – the ground plane; monumentality; and interplay of light and material – that I have been able to establish the essence of paulista brutalism.

The buildings that constitute paulista brutalism capture the qualities of outside. It does so by building an architectural space which is tied into the urban fabric and its context, as well as creating an atmosphere centred around the experience of the human being. The focus on light creates a juxtaposition between the heavy appearance of concrete and the openings allowing light to enter the building. It is the very creation of this relationship that is so unique in paulista brutalism

– where the heaviness of raw concrete is contrasted with deliberate openings for light, where the light is sculpted and treated as a material in itself as opposed to being all-pervasive. It is through these qualities that the architecture becomes more than just a space, but something which creates a dialogue with the outside and its users.

The three essential characteristics: the ground plane, monumentality and the relationship between light and material, combine to create an experience of the architecture. The experience that the essential characteristics create is very different to the purely visual and aesthetic qualities that Banham uses to define new brutalism. It is this very focus on experience, created by a relationship between the architecture and its surroundings, and the architecture and its users, that paulista brutalism differentiates itself from brutalism in Britain.

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